

See discussions, stats, and author profiles for this publication at: <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/377343640>

A cooperative coevolutionary hyper-heuristic approach to solve lot-sizing and job shop scheduling problems using genetic programming

Article in *International Journal of Production Research* · January 2024

DOI: 10.1080/00207543.2023.2301044

CITATIONS

10

READS

157

3 authors:

Yannik Zeiträg

Instituto Superior Técnico

7 PUBLICATIONS 74 CITATIONS

[SEE PROFILE](#)

José Rui Figueira

Instituto Superior Técnico - Universidade de Lisboa

159 PUBLICATIONS 14,797 CITATIONS

[SEE PROFILE](#)

Gonçalo Figueira

University of Porto

32 PUBLICATIONS 1,646 CITATIONS

[SEE PROFILE](#)

A cooperative coevolutionary hyper-heuristic approach to solve lot-sizing and job shop scheduling problems using genetic programming

Yannik Zeiträg^a, José Rui Figueira^a, and Gonçalo Figueira^b

^aCEGIST, Instituto Superior Técnico, Universidade de Lisboa, Av. Rovisco Pais 1, Lisbon 1049-001, Portugal;

^bINESC-TEC and Faculty of Engineering, University of Porto, Rua Dr Roberto Frias, Porto 4200-465, Portugal

ARTICLE HISTORY

Compiled April 14, 2023

ABSTRACT

Lot-sizing and scheduling in a job shop environment is a fundamental problem that appears in many industrial settings. The problem is very complex, and solutions are often needed fast. Although many solution methods have been proposed, with increasingly better results, their computational times are not suitable for decision-makers who want solutions instantly. Therefore, we propose a simulation-based greedy heuristic to efficiently generate production plans and schedules of good quality making use of priority rules. Using a selection of well-known rules from the literature, experiments on a variety of shop configurations and complexities showed that the proposed heuristic is able to obtain solutions with an average gap to CPLEX of 3.7%. To further improve the proposed heuristic, a cooperative coevolutionary genetic programming-based hyper-heuristic has been developed. The average gap to CPLEX was reduced up to 1.9%. These solutions are generated in a small fraction of a second, regardless of the size of the instance.

KEYWORDS

Lot-sizing; Job shop scheduling; Greedy heuristic; Hyper-heuristic; Genetic programming; Cooperative coevolution

1. Introduction

Lot-sizing and scheduling (LSS) in a job shop environment is a key problem of manufacturing companies, as it appears in many industrial settings. LSS decisions are interconnected decisions that should not be approached independently in order to achieve globally optimal solutions. Solution methods either use a hierarchical, iterative, or integrated strategy (Maravelias and Sung 2009). Hierarchical approaches usually suffer in finding overall optimal solutions and sometimes even lead to infeasible schedules due to missing capacity information of detailed schedules (Tan and Khoshnevis 2000; Shen, Wang, and Hao 2006). Although iterative approaches achieved promising results, they tend to converge to local optima (Gomez Urrutia, Aggoune, and Dauzère-Pérès 2014). Integrated solution methods are able to find global optimal or near-optimal solutions,

but are complex to implement and solve (Gomez Urrutia, Aggoune, and Dauzère-Pérès 2014).

LSS problems consist of a combination of NP-hard problems, which makes it difficult to find optimal solutions within a reasonable amount of time (Castro, Grossmann, and Zhang 2018). Moreover, in real-world scenarios, quick solution generation is crucial for frequent replanning due to dynamic events and fast decision-making. Solution time is also critical when interacting with decision support systems to iteratively generate different solutions - e.g. when considering multiple objectives (Miettinen, Ruiz, and Wierzbicki 2008).

The lot-sizing and job shop scheduling problem (LSJSSP) has been tackled since the 1980s (Afentakis 1985) and continues to receive attention (Giglio, Paolucci, and Roshani 2017). Dauzere-Peres and Lasserre (1994) introduced a mathematical model for multi-resource lot-sizing (LS) that included starting and completion times of operations in the formulation in order to consider job shop conditions. The problem was decomposed and solved iteratively by optimizing the LS problem and then finding the best schedule based on the resulting production plan. To solve large-scale problems, Gomez Urrutia, Aggoune, and Dauzère-Pérès (2014) proposed a combination of Lagrangian heuristic and Tabu search. Meanwhile, Wolosewicz, Dauzère-Pérès, and Aggoune (2015) considered a variant of the mathematical formulation that assumed a fixed sequence of operations. More recently, Abdollahzadeh Sangroudi and Ranjbar-Bourani (2021) proposed a self-adaptive Cuckoo optimization algorithm. All these heuristic approaches have been consistently improving computational times, but they still take tens to hundreds of seconds, even for moderate sized instances. These computational times are not congruent with the aforementioned practical settings, where decision makers want solutions instantly.

To the best of the authors' knowledge, there is currently no method that is able to find good solutions in less than a second. With this work, we concern to close this gap by developing a novel greedy heuristic for the integrated LSJSSP. Applying priority rules for both decisions regarding LS and JSS, the overall aim is to generate high quality solutions in short computational times for complex problem instances. Furthermore, we introduce a simulation-based cooperative coevolutionary genetic programming-based hyper-heuristic (CC-GP-HH) to automatically evolve priority rules within the proposed heuristic in order to improve its performance.

The main contributions of this work can be summarized as follows:

- The design of a simulation-based greedy heuristic for the LSJSSP based on priority rules;
- The development of a method to automatically evolve priority rules for the proposed heuristic to solve LSJSSP using simulation-based CC-GP-HH;
- Experiments to show the functionality and efficiency of the proposed greedy heuristic and the CC-GP-HH approach to further improve its performance.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section 2 provides an overview of related works. Section 3 briefly describes the problem at hand and presents its mathematical formulation. Section 4 contains the developed greedy heuristic for LSJSSPs as well as the simulation-based CC-GP-HH. Section 5 is dedicated to the experimental design, as well as the presentation and the discussion of the computational results. Section 6 concludes the achievements of this work and provides an outlook on promising future research directions.

2. Literature review

This literature review is separated into three subsections. The first part is devoted to greedy heuristics for LSS problems. The second part provides an overview of GP-HH approaches for LSS. The third part summarizes the literature review and elaborates the research gap that we intend to close with this work.

2.1. Greedy heuristics for lot-sizing and scheduling

For both decisions individually, greedy heuristics based on priority rules have shown to be able to efficiently find high-quality solutions. Due to their simplicity, ease of implementation, interpretability, and ability to solve large-scale problems, these methods are popular among researchers and practitioners. On the one hand, a cost saving index (CSI) can be used to describe potential cost savings for lot extensions during the construction or improvement of a production plan (Buschkühl et al. 2010). On the other hand, dispatching rules (DRs) are used to schedule jobs by prioritizing waiting operations and selecting the one to be processed next whenever a machine becomes idle (Panwalkar and Iskander 1977). Over the last decades, numerous CSIs and DRs have been developed (see, e.g., Dixon and Silver 1981; Eisenhut 1975; Blackstone, Phillips, and Hogg 1982; Pickardt and Branke 2012). Existing methods for both domains are discussed in the following sections.

2.1.1. Lot-sizing

With respect to LS decisions, greedy heuristics can be classified into constructive and improving heuristics (Buschkühl et al. 2010). Methods of the former category start from scratch and generate a production plan in a period-by-period manner. Representatives of the latter category typically start with an initial solution trying to successively reach cost improvements by iteratively increasing lot sizes. Recurring feasibility checks are necessary for both types of greedy heuristics. In fact, it can be distinguished between feedback and look-ahead mechanisms. However, what all of the above methods have in common is the use of CSIs to decide which lots to expand. Among many, frequently used CSIs for the LS decision are, i.e., Silver Meal (Silver and Meal 1973), Groff (Groff 1979), part-period balancing (DeMatteis 1968), and least unit cost. For a more comprehensive overview of greedy heuristics for LS problems, the interested reader is referred to the review by Buschkühl et al. (2010).

Eisenhut (1975) introduced the first constructive greedy heuristic for single-level LS problems. A priority index is assigned based on the part-period balancing rule. However, a feasibility check is missing and therefore the feasibility of the generated solution is not guaranteed. To overcome this issue, several approaches to implementing a feasibility routine were subsequently devised. Dixon and Silver (1981) proposed a look-ahead procedure to consider customer demands in future periods in form of required capacity. The comparison with the available capacity, taking into account the existing inventory, measures the feasibility of a production plan. In other words, the inventory needed to avoid future capacity bottlenecks can be determined. Lambrecht and Vanderveken (1979) and Dogramaci, Panayiotopoulos, and Adam (1981) employed a feedback mechanism to check feasibility. Whenever a capacity constraint is violated during the constructive procedure, production quantities are brought forward to earlier periods with residual capacity. Maes and Van Wassenhove (1986) developed 72 algorithms in their ABC heuristic, each of them representing a combination of dif-

ferent priority indices for ordering items, cost criteria for extending lots, and search strategies. Gupta and Magnusson (2005) extended the greedy constructive procedure by considering setup times for single-stage LS problems.

Another group of researches focused on the development of improvement greedy heuristics, the second category of greedy heuristics for LS. Starting from an initial, mostly infeasible inferior solution, which is usually generated by unrestricted heuristics such as the Wagner-Within (Wagner and Whitin 1958) or lot-for-lot (L4L) method, this type of greedy heuristics strive iteratively for better feasible solutions. Examples for improvement heuristics regarding single-level LS can be found in (Karni and Roll 1982; Günther 1987). Van Nunen and Wessels (1978) and Trigeiro (1989) included the consideration of setup times.

A possible way to expand greedy heuristics to multi-level LS problems is the simplification of the problem making use of decomposition and aggregation approaches. While aggregation approaches aim to generate solutions in a bottom-up manner, decomposition approaches separate the original problem into sub-problems. Both types of methods seek to reduce the problem size in such a way to solve the multi-level LS problem with modified versions of the single-level greedy heuristics. Boctor and Poulin (2005) introduced an aggregation heuristic for a multi-level LS problem with same lot-sizes on each stage of the production system and under assumption of a flow shop environment. The aggregated single-level problems are proposed to solve via an improvement greedy heuristic. Starting with a solution initialized by the L4L approach, the first step aims to reach feasibility by shifting exceeding capacity forward to earlier periods. Otherwise, if all demands can be fulfilled within the capacity limitations and residual capacity remains, lot-sizes are attempted to increase. Three different cost saving indices are implemented and tested for the selection of the lot to be expanded.

Tempelmeier and Helber (1994) decomposed the multi-level LS problem into a sequence of single-level sub-problems. A modified version of the Dixon-Silver heuristic was proposed to construct solutions periodwise. The feasibility check was extended to consider the multiple levels of the problem. The authors tested the developed algorithm for different configurations of the determination of cost parameters and the ordering of the product/operation structure. An extension regarding the incorporation of setup costs has been elaborated by Helber (1995).

2.1.2. Scheduling

A well-known greedy heuristic to approximate good solutions for scheduling problems can be realized through dispatching rules (DRs) (Blackstone, Phillips, and Hogg 1982; Panwalkar and Iskander 1977). Due to their simplicity, interpretability, and ease of implementation, DRs are among the most frequently studied heuristics in the scheduling research community. Moreover, practitioners appreciate their fast execution which facilitates the application for large-scale real-world problems and even allows solving complex problems in real-time. Due to their reactive abilities, DRs revealed to be particularly useful to encounter the appearance of unforeseen events such as the case of dynamic JSS problems. Whenever a machine becomes idle, a DR assigns a priority index to all jobs waiting. The job with the highest priority is then selected to be processed next. DRs can be classified into simple priority rules, composite DRs, and weighted priority indices (Panwalkar and Iskander 1977). Most prominent examples of simple priority rules are the *shortest processing time first* (SPT), and *first-in-first-out* (FIFO). Combining simple priority rules leads to more complex but also more sophisticated composite DRs such as *process time plus work-in-next-queue* (PT+WINQ) (Holthaus

and Rajendran 1997). Weighted priority indices are linear combinations of simple priority rules (Jayamohan and Rajendran 2004). As a typical application, weights can be employed to strive for a desired compromise solutions between two or more conflicting objectives (Dabbas and Fowler 2003). Other classifications further distinguish DRs with respect to the characteristics of their parameter(s) between dynamic and static or local and global rules (Moore and Wilson 1967).

As one of the main drawbacks of DRs, their performance showed to be dependent on the specific conditions of particular problems. Therefore, no rule exists that is superior in any situation and regarding all criteria (Rajendran and Holthaus 1999). Rather, individual rules must be designed to attain appropriate results for specific requirements. A comparative study of DRs in different JSS environments can be found, e.g., in Panwalkar and Iskander (1977) Blackstone, Phillips, and Hogg (1982), and Rajendran and Holthaus (1999).

2.2. Genetic programming hyper-heuristics for lot-sizing and scheduling

The design of the priority rules within the aforementioned greedy heuristics has traditionally been carried out in a tedious trial-and-error process by experts with a comprehensive knowledge of the problem (Geiger, Uzsoy, and Aytuğ 2006). Recently, GP-HH has been emerged as a promising method to automatically evolve heuristics making use of machine learning techniques (see, e.g., Hein et al. 2018; Branke et al. 2016). Instead of searching directly on the search space of solutions, HH typically use evolutionary-based algorithms to operate on a search space of heuristics or heuristic components (Burke et al. 2003). As a special version of a genetic algorithm, GP combines the concepts of evolutionary computation and automatic programming, which makes the method particularly useful to evolve mathematical expressions such as priority rules (Koza 1992). Several GP-HH approaches for the automatic design of heuristics for various types of scheduling problems have been published in the past 20 years. The interested reader is referred to the surveys by Branke et al. (2016), and Nguyen, Mei, and Zhang (2017).

An early approach to automatically evolve DRs via GP-HH was provided by Dimopoulos and Zalzalá (2001). Starting from low complexity, the authors considered a single-machine scheduling problem. Abednego and Hendratmo (2011) extended the single-machine problem to a bi-objective optimization problem that is proposed to be solved making use of the weighted-sum approach. Jakobović, Jelenković, and Budin (2007) further increased the complexity of the shop configuration to a parallel-machine shop scheduling problem. Masood et al. (2017) address static JSS problems under consideration of multiple objectives. The authors proposed the well-known multi-objective evolutionary algorithm NSGA-III to obtain non-dominated solutions. In their approach, Ho and Tay (2005) considered a flexible JSS problem. Besides the scheduling decision, flexible JSS problems include a second decision regarding the machine assignment. Tay and Ho (2008) modified the aforementioned algorithm to handle multiple objectives via the weighted-sum approach. Early approaches evolve DRs for the scheduling decision while assuming a fixed priority rule for the machine assignment (Ho and Tay 2005; Tay and Ho 2008). Later, GP-HH methods have been developed to simultaneously evolve rules for both decisions making use of CC-GP with two sub-populations or GP with two sub-trees (Zhou, Yang, and Huang 2020).

Known for their ease of use and speed of execution, DRs enable reactive adaptation to unforeseen events. Therefore and due to the high relevance for real industrial cases,

recent research activities focus on dynamic JSS problems. Numerous approaches to different requirements have been developed, i.e., regarding a single objective (Pickardt et al. 2013; Park et al. 2018; Ferreira, Figueira, and Amorim 2022), considering multiple objectives (Nguyen et al. 2013; Zeiträg et al. 2022), and including flexible machine assignment decisions (Zhou, Yang, and Huang 2020; Zhang, Mei, and Zhang 2019). A comprehensive review of methods to automatically design heuristics for scheduling problems can be found in Branke et al. (2016).

Although a priority rule similar to the DR is employed for greedy heuristics regarding LS, the literature on the automated generation of those CSIs for LS is scarce. Only a single approach was found, in which Hein et al. (2018) employed a GP algorithm to automatically evolve CSIs within a greedy heuristic for the well-known capacitated LS problem. Experimental results showed that their method is able to find solutions superior to other benchmark rules. However, as their approach is based on the classical Dixon-Silver heuristic (Dixon and Silver 1981), only LS problems regarding a single resource are considered.

2.3. *Summary*

Constructive greedy heuristics based on priority rules can be used to quickly approximate good solutions for LS problems. Yet, there is a lack of efficient greedy heuristics for integrated LSS problems, particularly under consideration of complex JSS settings. To address this gap, a novel method is needed to find near-optimal solutions for large-scale LSJSSPs in short computational time. This is particularly important for manufacturing companies facing increasing complexity due to a large number of product variants and flexible production systems in a growing dynamic environment.

In fact, priority rules within greedy heuristics are typically not universally superior. Problem-specific rules must be designed using either expert knowledge or machine learning techniques. GP-HH is a successful method for automatically learning mathematical formulations, including priority rules for dynamic scheduling problems. However, research on LS is scarce, and no investigation has been conducted on multi-resource LS or LSJSSPs.

To address the aforementioned gaps in the literature, this work presents a novel approach to automatically search for efficient rules within a greedy heuristic using a combination of evolutionary techniques, machine learning concepts, and simulation. To the best of the authors' knowledge, this is the first attempt to introduce such a method for solving complex LSJSSPs.

3. **Problem formulation**

The LSJSSP consists of a set of products, a set of machines, and a set of periods. LSJSSP, as many other LS models, aims to determine production quantities *per* product and period in such a way that the total costs are minimized. Several cost aspects have been studied in the literature, while in this work we focus on minimizing the production, inventory holding, and setup costs. The demands *per* product and period are given and must be fulfilled at the end of the corresponding period. Backlogs are not allowed. Whenever a product is planned to be manufactured in a period, a setup must be carried out which entails costs and time. Assuming that at most one lot of each product is defined for each period, for scheduling purposes the lots can also be denoted as jobs. Each job contains a set of sequential operations while each operation

is assigned to one machine. The sequence of the operations (routings) is predefined and invariant. Each job has a release date and due date associated with the assigned period. Each operation has a processing time. Furthermore, a feasible solution must comply with the following conditions:

- Preemption of operations is not allowed;
- Each machine can execute at most one operation at a time;
- All machines are always available and ready for processing operations whenever they become idle.

The sets, indices, parameters, and variables for the mathematical formulation of the problem under consideration are denoted as follows:

Indices and sets:

- i : Index of products, $i = 1, \dots, n$,
- ℓ : Index of periods, $\ell = 1, \dots, u$
- r : Index of machines, $r = 1, \dots, q$
- \mathcal{R} : Set of pairs of machines associated to consecutive operations in the routing of jobs

Parameters:

- p_{ir} : Processing time *per* unit of product i on machine r
- s_{ir} : Setup time of product i on machine r
- a_ℓ : Available capacity of period ℓ (period length)
- c_i^s : Setup costs of product i
- c_i^p : Production costs *per* unit of product i
- c_i^h : Holding costs *per* unit of product i
- $d_{i\ell}$: Demand for product i in period ℓ
- y_{i0} : Initial inventory of product i

Variables:

- $x_{i\ell}$: Production quantity (lotsize) of product i in period ℓ
- $y_{i\ell}$: Inventory of product i at the end of period ℓ
- $t_{ir\ell}^s$: Start time of product i on machine r in period ℓ

Binary variables:

- $z_{i\ell}$: Setup state; $z_{i\ell} = 1$, if setup for product i in period ℓ (0 otherwise)
- $w_{i'ir\ell}$: Sequence state; $w_{i'ir\ell} = 1$, if product i is produced after product i' on machine r in period ℓ (0 otherwise)

The LSJSSP adopted from Dauzere-Peres and Lasserre (1994), and Gomez Urrutia, Aggoune, and Dauzère-Pérès (2014) can be formulated as follows:

$$\min f(x, y, z) = \sum_{\ell=1}^u \sum_{i=1}^n \left(c_i^p x_{i\ell} + c_i^h y_{i\ell} + c_i^s z_{i\ell} \right) \quad (1)$$

s.t.:

$$y_{i\ell} = y_{i(\ell-1)} + x_{i\ell} - d_{i\ell}, \quad i = 1, \dots, n, \ell = 1, \dots, u \quad (2)$$

$$t_{i'r\ell}^s \geq t_{i'r\ell}^s + p_{i'r} x_{i\ell} + s_{i'r} z_{i\ell}, \quad i = 1, \dots, n, \ell = 1, \dots, u, \quad (3)$$

$$\forall (r, r') \in \mathcal{R}$$

$$t_{i'r\ell}^s \geq t_{i'r\ell}^s + p_{i'r} x_{i\ell} + s_{i'r} z_{i\ell} - M w_{i'irl}, \quad i, i' = 1, \dots, n, i \neq i', \quad (4)$$

$$\ell = 1, \dots, u, r = 1, \dots, q$$

$$t_{i'r\ell}^s \geq t_{i'r\ell}^s + p_{i'r} x_{i\ell} + s_{i'r} z_{i\ell} - M(1 - w_{i'irl}), \quad i, i' = 1, \dots, n, i \neq i', \quad (5)$$

$$\ell = 1, \dots, u, r = 1, \dots, q$$

$$w_{i'irl} + w_{i'ir\ell} = 1, \quad i, i' = 1, \dots, n, i \neq i', \quad (6)$$

$$\ell = 1, \dots, u, r = 1, \dots, q$$

$$t_{i'r\ell}^s + p_{i'r} x_{i\ell} + s_{i'r} z_{i\ell} \leq a_{\ell}, \quad i = 1, \dots, n, \ell = 1, \dots, u, \quad (7)$$

$$r = 1, \dots, q$$

$$x_{i\ell} \leq \left(\sum_{\ell_1=\ell}^u d_{i\ell_1} \right) z_{i\ell}, \quad i = 1, \dots, n, \ell = 1, \dots, u \quad (8)$$

$$x_{i\ell}, y_{i\ell} \geq 0, \quad i = 1, \dots, n, \ell = 1, \dots, u \quad (9)$$

$$t_{i'r\ell}^s \geq 0, \quad i = 1, \dots, n, \ell = 1, \dots, u, \quad (10)$$

$$r = 1, \dots, q$$

$$z_{i\ell} \in \{0, 1\}, \quad i = 1, \dots, n, \ell = 1, \dots, u \quad (11)$$

$$w_{i'irl} \in \{0, 1\}, \quad i, i' = 1, \dots, n, i \neq i', \quad (12)$$

$$\ell = 1, \dots, u, r = 1, \dots, q$$

Equation (1) represents the objective function of the LSJSSP. It considers the minimization of the sum of all production, setup, and inventory holding costs over the entire planning horizon. Equation (2) represents the inventory balance constraint and guarantees a sufficient production of products to satisfy the demands. Equation (3), Equation (4), Equation (5), and Equation (6) are responsible for taking care of the sequence of operations in the routings and on the machines. Equation (7) ensure that the production is completed withing the available capacity of a period. Equation (8) allows a production of a product only in periods where a setup of that product takes place. Equation (9) and Equation (10) ensure the non-negativity of the production quantity, inventory, and start time of production. Equation (11) and Equation (12) defines the binary setup and sequence variable.

4. Methodology

This section is separated into two parts. First, we introduce a novel simulation-based greedy heuristic to efficiently provide good solutions for the LSJSSP. In the second part of this section, we present an overview of the proposed CC-GP-HH framework to coevolve priority rules for LS and JSS decisions within the developed greedy heuristic.

In particular, we discuss the individual modules of the framework with the focus on the innovative parts of the CC-GP-HH module and the simulation-based fitness evaluation of the evolving LSS priority rules.

4.1. *A greedy heuristic for lot-sizing and job shop scheduling*

Due to its simplicity and efficiency, the Dixon-Silver heuristic (Dixon and Silver 1981) is among the most popular greedy heuristics for LS problems. However, the Dixon-Silver heuristic is originally designed to consider single resource problems. Since the LSJSSP that this work intends to solve contains multiple resources, the simple Dixon-Silver heuristic cannot be considered as suitable basis. Tempelmeier and Helber (1994) developed a modified version of the Dixon-Silver heuristic that allows to take multiple resources into account by decomposing the problem and considering the LS decisions sequentially for each resource. Although the authors proposed a feasibility routine across all resources, due to its period-by-period and resource-by-resource constructive behavior this method seems also not be sufficient for taking care of the complex JSS constraints. For our purpose, the improvement algorithm introduced by Boctor and Poulin (2005) represents the most promising approach and serves therefore as the starting point for the development of the heuristic for LSJSSP. In particular, the fact that this procedure directly starts with an initial solution allows us to construct detailed schedules from the beginning which is crucial to consistently ensure feasibility through simulation.

The proposed procedure can be separated into two main steps. In the first step, an initial production plan must be created. After validation of the feasibility, an attempt is made to either improve or smooth the production plan in the second step. If all demands can be satisfied and residual capacity (a^r) exists, a procedure to increase lot-sizes with the aim of reducing the total costs is carried out. Otherwise, if the available capacity in the investigated period is not sufficient to cover all demands, a backtracking mechanism is activated in order to restore feasibility. This procedure is repeated for every period. One of the main novelties compared to the original publication represents the simulation-based feasibility check in which we propose to use priority rules and discrete event simulation (DES) to construct detailed schedules. A general overview of the greedy heuristic is shown in Algorithm 1.

The main input of the proposed greedy heuristic represents an LSJSSP instance containing all required information regarding the shop configuration such as the number of products, machines, and periods as well as problem-specific details such as the processing time, setup time, setup cost, production cost, holding cost, demands, routings, and initial inventory *per* product. A final production plan containing the production quantity *per* product and period as well as the detailed schedules *per* period including the start time *per* product and machine are considered the main outcome of the procedure. The five main modules regarding the generation of an initial solution, the increasing of lot sizes, the backtracking of production quantities, the feasibility check, and the generation of the final schedules are introduced in the following.

– GENERATE INITIAL PRODUCTION PLAN

This procedure is dedicated to generating an initial solution. Inspired by the L4L method, the proposed algorithm defines the production quantities *per* product of the period under consideration based on the associated net demands. The net demands *per* product can be calculated as the difference between the actual demands and the inventory carried over from the previous period. The pseudocode

Algorithm 1 Greedy heuristic for LSJSSP

Input: Test instance I , Lot-sizing rule LSR , Job sequencing rule JSR

Output: A production plan P and detailed schedules S

```
1:  $P \leftarrow \{\}$ 
2:  $S \leftarrow \{\}$ 
3: for  $\ell = 1$  to  $u$  do
4:    $P \leftarrow$  GENERATE INITIAL PRODUCTION PLAN
5:    $a_\ell^r \leftarrow$  FEASIBILITY CHECK ▷ Apply JSR
6:   if  $a_\ell^r > 0$  then
7:      $P \leftarrow$  INCREASE LOT SIZES PROCEDURE ▷ Apply LSR
8:   else
9:      $P \leftarrow$  BACKTRACK MECHANISM
10:  end if
11: end for
12:  $S \leftarrow$  GENERATE FINAL SCHEDULES
13: Return  $P, S$ 
```

of the proposed procedure is presented in Algorithm 2.

Algorithm 2 Generate initial production plan

Input: Period ℓ , Instance I

Output: Set of production quantities X

```
1:  $X \leftarrow \{\}$ 
2: for  $i = 1$  to  $n$  do
3:    $x_{i\ell} = d_{i\ell} - y_{i\ell-1}$ 
4:    $X \cup \{x_{i\ell}\}$ 
5: end for
6: Return  $X$ 
```

– INCREASE LOT SIZES PROCEDURE

In case residual capacity exists in the considered period after generating the initial production plan, potentially cost saving through lot-size increases are investigated. First, the estimated cost savings are calculated for all products under the consideration of producing demands earlier making use of a CSI. The demand with the highest estimated cost savings is then selected to be included in the lot of the current period. A feasibility check is subsequently required to ensure the capacity limits across all machines keep respected. If that is not the case, the lot extension is withdrawn. This procedure is repeated for all future demands that have a positive CSI, which indicates a potential cost saving. The LSJSSP definition in this study assumes that all components of a product must be produced within the same period. Therefore, only the entire production of a product (including all operations) can be considered for the lot-size increase. The pseudocode of the proposed procedure is shown in Algorithm 3.

– BACKTRACKING MECHANISM

The purpose of the backtracking mechanism is to restore feasibility by shifting production quantities to earlier periods in case the period in which the actual demand is needed does not provide sufficient capacity. In the first step of the backtracking procedure, all production quantities of the infeasible period are reset to zero. In the next step, all products planned to be produced are sorted based

Algorithm 3 Increase lot size procedure

Input: Period ℓ , Instance I , Lot-sizing rule LSR , Job sequencing rule JSR

Output: Set of production quantities $X = \{x_{0\ell}, \dots, x_{i\ell}, \dots, x_{n\ell}\}$

```
1:  $L \leftarrow \{\}$ 
2: for  $\ell_1 = \ell + 1$  to  $u$  do
3:   for  $i = 1$  to  $n$  do
4:     if  $d_{i\ell_1} \neq 0$  then
5:        $CSI \leftarrow LSR(i, \ell_1)$  ▷ Apply LSR
6:       if  $CSI > 0$  then
7:          $L \cup \{CSI\}$ 
8:       end if
9:     end if
10:  end for
11: end for
12: Sort  $L$  in descending order
13: foreach  $(i, \ell_1) \in L$  do
14:    $X \leftarrow X \setminus \{x_{i\ell}\}$ 
15:    $x_{i\ell} \leftarrow x_{i\ell} + d_{i\ell_1}$ 
16:    $a_\ell^r \leftarrow \text{FEASIBILITY CHECK}$  ▷ Apply JSR
17:   if  $a_\ell^r < 0$  then
18:      $x_{i\ell} \leftarrow x_{i\ell} - d_{i\ell_1}$  ▷ Withdraw the lot extension, if infeasible
19:   end if
20:    $X \leftarrow X \cup \{x_{i\ell}\}$ 
21:    $y_{i\ell} \leftarrow y_{i\ell-1} + x_{i\ell} - d_{i\ell}$  ▷ Update inventory
22: end for
23: Return  $X$ 
```

on their unit holding costs in descending order. Starting from the first element, all products are step by step assigned to the period. Whenever a production quantity is assigned, another feasibility check must be carried out to validate if the capacity restriction is not violated. In the case of exceeding the available capacity, the assigned lot is withdrawn. This procedure is repeated until all products have been checked. The remaining products, which could not be assigned to the current period without exceeding the capacity limit, are then selected to be produced in earlier periods with enough residual capacity. Therefore, in the first step, the exceeding production quantities are checked to be added on already existing lots in order to avoid additional setup costs. If unassigned production quantities still remain after that, the generation of new lots in earlier periods are investigated for preproduction. The pseudocode of the backtracking mechanism can be found in Algorithm 4.

Algorithm 4 Backtrack mechanism

Input: Period ℓ , Instance I , Job sequencing rule JSR **Output:** Set of production quantities $X = \{x_{0\ell}, \dots, x_{i\ell}, \dots, x_{n\ell}\}$

```
1:  $x_{i\ell} \leftarrow 0, \forall i$ 
2:  $P = \{i \mid (d_{i\ell} - y_{i\ell-1}) > 0\}$ 
3: Sort  $P$  in descending order of inventory holding costs per unit
4: foreach  $i \in P$  do
5:    $x_{i\ell} \leftarrow x_{i\ell} + d_{i\ell} - y_{i\ell-1}$ 
6:    $a_{\ell_1}^r \leftarrow$  FEASIBILITY CHECK ▷ Apply JSR
7:   if  $a_{\ell_1}^r \geq 0$  then
8:      $\bar{P} \leftarrow P \setminus \{i\}$ 
9:   else
10:     $x_{i\ell} \leftarrow x_{i\ell} - d_{i\ell} + y_{i\ell-1}$  ▷ Withdraw the lot assignment, if infeasible
11:   end if
12: end for
13: foreach  $i \in P$  do ▷ Move production quantities back to existing lots
14:    $\ell_1 = \ell - 1$ 
15:   while  $(d_{i\ell} - y_{i\ell-1}) > 0 \vee \ell_1 \geq 0$  do
16:     if  $x_{i\ell_1} > 0$  then ▷ Check if a lot already exists
17:        $x_{i\ell_1} \leftarrow x_{i\ell_1} + d_{i\ell} - y_{i\ell-1}$ 
18:        $a_{\ell_1}^r \leftarrow$  FEASIBILITY CHECK ▷ Apply JSR
19:       if  $a_{\ell_1}^r \geq 0$  then
20:          $\bar{P} \leftarrow P \setminus \{i\}$ 
21:       else
22:          $x_{i\ell_1} \leftarrow x_{i\ell_1} - d_{i\ell} + y_{i\ell-1}$  ▷ Withdraw the lot assignment, if infeasible
23:       end if
24:        $y_{i\ell} \leftarrow y_{i\ell-1} + x_{i\ell} - d_{i\ell}$  ▷ Update inventory
25:     end if
26:      $\ell_1 \leftarrow \ell_1 - 1$ 
27:   end while
28: end for
29: foreach  $i \in P$  do ▷ Generate new lots for the exceeding production quantities
30:    $\ell_1 = \ell - 1$ 
31:   while  $(d_{i\ell} - y_{i\ell-1}) > 0 \vee \ell_1 \geq 0$  do
32:     if  $x_{i\ell_1} = 0$  then ▷ Ensure that no lot already exists
33:        $x_{i\ell_1} \leftarrow x_{i\ell_1} + d_{i\ell} - y_{i\ell-1}$ 
34:        $a_{\ell_1}^r \leftarrow$  FEASIBILITY CHECK ▷ Apply JSR
35:       if  $a_{\ell_1}^r \geq 0$  then
36:          $\bar{P} \leftarrow P \setminus \{i\}$ 
37:       else
38:          $x_{i\ell_1} \leftarrow x_{i\ell_1} - d_{i\ell} + y_{i\ell-1}$  ▷ Withdraw the lot assignment, if infeasible
39:       end if
40:        $y_{i\ell} \leftarrow y_{i\ell-1} + x_{i\ell} - d_{i\ell}$  ▷ Update inventory
41:     end if
42:      $\ell_1 \leftarrow \ell_1 - 1$ 
43:   end while
44: end for
45: Return  $X$ 
```

– FEASIBILITY CHECK

The feasibility check is responsible for evaluating whether the previously determined production quantities can be scheduled without exceeding the available capacity or not. Instead of the flow shop configuration that has been investigated in the original publication, we intend to solve a more complex JSS environment. Since for the JSS operations of different products share the same machines, it is not possible to estimate the required capacity precisely enough just by summing up the processing times, which usually leads to an underestimation of the actually required capacity. Due to the complexity of the JSS configuration, we propose to generate detailed schedules making use of DES. This process of creating detailed schedules represents one of the main differences to the original proposed heuristic and can therefore be highlighted as the most innovative aspects of the developed greedy heuristic that allows to solve complex JSS configurations. The production quantities *per* product and period can be translated into jobs. These jobs can further be dissolved into operations using the routing information of the corresponding instance. The DES can then construct the schedule by releasing operations whenever the predecessor has been completed and prioritizing waiting operations whenever a machine becomes idle. In order to evaluate the feasibility, the makespan of the schedule can be derived and compared to the available capacity after finishing the simulation run. The difference of both represents the residual capacity, which is the main outcome of this procedure. More details of the DES are introduced in Section 4.2.2.

– GENERATE FINAL SCHEDULES

For generating the final schedules, we propose to use the same DES as explained above. The main difference is that instead of returning the residual capacity, this procedure returns all relevant information about the schedules such as starting and completion times of jobs and operations. This step is also essential as the production quantities of already determined periods might be manipulated by the backtracking mechanism along the entire procedure. To consider these changes, the schedules of all periods must be updated at the end of the heuristic.

4.2. *The simulation-based CC-GP-HH framework for lot-sizing and job shop scheduling problems*

The proposed framework consists of two modules, the CC-GP-HH-based LSS policy (LSSP) generator and the constructive simulation-based fitness evaluator (see Figure 1). The CC-GP-HH-based LSSP generator is where the actual GP takes place. The procedure starts by generating the initial populations. For each of the LSS decisions, one sub-population is initialized. Each sub-population contains either lot-sizing rules (LSR) or job sequencing rules (JSR). The combination of both is referred to below as LSSP. There are various ways in how individuals can collaborate (see Section 5.1.4). The fitness of each individual (LSSP) is evaluated using the responsible simulation module within the proposed framework. Period by period, lot-sizes are determined, and detailed schedules are created and improved by applying the developed greedy heuristic (see Section 4.1). Within the constructive process, potential cost-saving lot extensions are carried out employing the LSR and detailed schedules are prepared with the purpose of validating the feasibility of candidate solutions via JSR. To efficiently generate the schedules, a DES is carried out. This step is crucial in order to evaluate the feasibility of scheduling the production plan. The fitness of an individual is usually

Figure 1. Proposed framework.

computed as the mean performance of a set of training instances. Based on their fitness, individuals are ranked and selected to create offspring individuals using classical evolutionary operators such as mutation and crossover. After updating the population the whole procedure is repeated until the maximum number of generations is reached. When the stopping criterion is met, the best-performing individual is returned by the CC-GP-HH-based LSSP generator and the procedure is finished.

4.2.1. The CC-GP-HH module

Both priority rules, the one for lot extension decisions and the one for scheduling decisions can be simultaneously and automatically generated employing CC techniques. For flexible dynamic JSS problems, the subpopulation formulations have already been shown to successfully coevolve two rules for two interconnected decisions (in this case regarding the machine assignment and the scheduling (Zhou, Yang, and Huang 2020)). Following the same idea, we propose a CC-GP-HH framework to automatically generate priority rules to select lots for extension and create schedules in such a way that the total costs are optimized. Figure 2 shows the decoding technique of an individual in the proposed CC procedure.

4.2.2. The simulation module

For the fitness evaluation of the individuals (LSSP), we propose to use DES. The aim of this module is to convert the input data (demand matrix) into a production plan, based on which detailed schedules can be generated. For this purpose, the proposed greedy heuristic presented in Section 4.1 is carried out. Within this improving pro-

Figure 2. Cooperative coevolution decoding scheme.

cedure, lot extensions are carried out based on the LSR component of the individual to be evaluated. Whenever a lot is changed, the feasibility of the resulting production plan must be validated. Therefore, the production plan describing the quantities *per* product and period is used for preparing detailed schedules. To this end, the production quantities are translated to jobs consisting of operations, which are scheduled using the JSR component of the individual under consideration. During the simulation run, whenever a machine becomes idle, the operation with the highest priority according to the JSR is selected to be processed next. Based on the detailed schedules, the feasibility can be evaluated and further adjustments, if any, might be conducted along with the algorithm's expiration.

5. Computational experiments

This section is structured in three parts. First, we introduce how the experiments are designed. The second subsection shows the results of executed experiments, which are subsequently summarized and discussed in the third part of this section.

5.1. Experimental design

The design for the computational experiments is presented in the following. In particular, we first introduce the generation of the problem instances. The second part is devoted to the selection of terminals and functions for the composition of the evolving rules. The third part presents the comparing algorithms for the evaluation of the proposed methods' performances. The last part includes a series of preliminary experiments for determining the most significant parameters of the CC-GP-HH algorithm.

The proposed CC-GP-HH framework has been implemented in JAVA making use of

Table 1. LSJSSP instances adapted from Gomez Urrutia, Aggoune, and Dauzère-Pérès (2014).

	n	q	u	ct	$d_{i\ell}$	s_{ir}	c_i^s	c_i^p	c_i^h
FT06	6	6	5	0.46	[3,8]	10	30	4	1
			10	0.46	[3,8]	10	30	4	1
			20	0.46	[2,5]	10	30	4	1
FT10	10	10	5	0.44	[3,8]	10	30	4	1
			10	0.50	[3,8]	10	30	4	1
			20	0.58	[2,5]	10	20	4	1
FT20	20	5	5	0.44	[3,8]	10	30	4	1
			10	0.48	[3,8]	10	30	4	1
			20	0.54	[5,10]	10	25	4	1

the evolutionary computation toolkit *ECJ* (Luke 1998) for the CC and GP operations¹. The optimization models were solved using *IBM ILOG CPLEX Optimization Studio 12.10.0*. All experiments have been carried out on a standard Laptop with an Intel Core i5-8250U CPU @1.60 GHz and 16 GB of RAM.

5.1.1. Problem instances

To evaluate the performance of the proposed CC-GP-HH method, an adequate test bed is required to train and validate evolving LSSPs. Since the literature on LSJSSP is quite scarce, there are no established standard problems yet (Rohaninejad, Janota, and Hanzálek 2023). However, Gomez Urrutia, Aggoune, and Dauzère-Pérès (2014) modified the well-known JSS problems defined by Fisher and Thompson (1963) and extended them to meet LSJSSP requirements. JSS instances of different complexity and size, varying from six products and six machines to 20 products and five machines, form the basis for generating the training and validation problems. Please note that only full shop configurations are considered which means each product must visit each machine exactly once. The number of operations is therefore equal to the number of machines. The processing time per operation is randomly determined in a range between 1 and 10. The sequence of the machines to be visited is randomly determined *per* product.

While the required scheduling information is provided by the original JSS test instances from Fisher and Thompson (1963), additional parameters have to be defined to consider the LS aspect. As proposed by Gomez Urrutia, Aggoune, and Dauzère-Pérès (2014), the number of periods u , the capacity tightness ct , the demand *per* product and period $d_{i\ell}$, the setup times *per* product and machine s_{ir} , the setup costs *per* product c_i^s , the production costs *per* product c_i^p , and the holding costs *per* product c_i^h must be added to generate suitable instances for the LSJSSP. In order to provide a wide range of size and complexity, instances are proposed to be randomly generated following a uniform distribution of the demand *per* product and period. Please note that the capacity tightness determines the available capacity based on the required capacity according to the sum of processing times to satisfy all demands and all setup times. A summary of all information used to generate training and validation instances is presented in Table 1. Therefore, we have a set of in total nine different instance classes that we consider for the following experiments.

¹The repository of the project including all parameter and instance files can be found here: <https://github.com/YZeit/LSJSS>

5.1.2. *Terminals and functions*

Determining the set of terminals and functions is considered another crucial decision for the CC-GP-HH framework. The size of the set of terminals and functions significantly influences the computational complexity of searching for the best-performing individual. Therefore, only the most relevant operators, parameters, and variables should be considered. However, since this work represents the first attempt to automatically evolve priority rules for the proposed greedy heuristic to solve LSJSSPs, we suggest investigating a broad variety of functions and terminals. To this end, the most common mathematical, arithmetic, and logical operators have been selected as the functions, and parameters and variables of existing priority rules for LS and JSS (see Table 2) have been selected as the terminals of the CC-GP-HH method. Note that the ternary “if-then-else” operator has been included as Nguyen, Mei, and Zhang (2017) showed its contribution to reaching complex objectives in JSS environments. Furthermore, the list has been extended based on the works by Hein et al. (2018) and Zeiträg et al. (2022). An overview of all terminals and functions can be found in Table A1 in the Appendix.

5.1.3. *Comparing algorithms*

For the evaluation of the performance of the developed CC-GP-HH algorithm, we propose to compare the results to the optimum of the MIP from Section 3. Therefore, we implemented the MIP in CPLEX and configured a time limit of one hour. An overview of the results can be found in Table B1 in the Appendix. Note that the optimal solution could not be obtained for all instances, but the optimality gap is always within 4%.

Furthermore, as the main purpose of our approach is to evolve better-performing priority rules for LS and JSS decisions than the already existing ones, we propose to compare the evolved rules to well-known rules from the literature. A selection of the five most prominent representatives from both domains has been collected and implemented in our greedy heuristic introduced in Section 4.1. In addition, a random selection is added to both lists of candidates. Pairing all these rules results in a total of 36 combinations that have been run on all instances. More details about the performance of the existing rules within the proposed greedy heuristic are shown in Table C1 in the Appendix.

5.1.4. *Cooperative coevolutionary genetic programming configuration*

GP algorithms contain a series of crucial parameters that should be carefully configured in order to achieve reasonable results. Although the focus of this work is not to fine-tune every parameter until reaching the best possible performance, we carried out preliminary experiments on the most significant parameters, namely the training set size, the population size, and the number of generations. Furthermore, another interesting aspect with regard to this work represents the strategy of collaborating individuals of each subpopulation within the CC-GP-HH framework. Therefore, we tested different collaboration schemes that are either based on randomness or the fitness of individuals from the previous generation. For computational reasons, instances from the class of FT06 have been chosen and investigated for all preliminary experiments. All the aforementioned parameters have a significant effect on the computational most demanding part of the entire algorithm, the number of fitness evaluations (FEs). An FE includes the execution of one individual on one problem instance applying the

Table 2. Benchmark priority rules.

Type	Name	Formulation
JSR	Shortest Processing Time (SPT)	PT
	First-In-First-Out (FIFO)	RTO
	Most Total Work Remaining (MTWR)	RPT
	Work In Next Queue (WINQ)	$WINQ$
	Sum of shortest processing time and work in next queue (PT+WINQ)	$PT + WINQ$
	Random (R)	Random selection of products
LSR		$\frac{BSV * SC + HCC}{NPRC} - \frac{SC + HCC + AHC}{NPRE}$
	Dixon-Silver (DS)	$\frac{CU * PLE}{NPRC^2 * PLE}$
	Eisenhut (E)	$\frac{BSV * SC - HCC - AHC}{NPRC^2 * PLE}$
	Groff (GR)	$\frac{2 * BSV * SC}{HC} - PLE * NPRC * NPRE$
	Least-Unit Cost (LUC)	$\frac{BSV * SC + HCC}{CLS} - \frac{SC + HCC + AHC}{CLS + PLE}$
	Absolute Cost (AC)	$BSV * SC - AHC$
	Random (R)	Random selection of products

proposed greedy heuristic. A limit of 500,000 FEs is specified in order to ensure a fair comparison and keep the computing time for the training of new rules within reasonable limits. Furthermore, the results of the following experiments are presented as the gap to the solutions obtained by CPLEX. Despite the aforementioned parameters to be investigated in the following, the remaining GP parameters are rather standard and not part of further examinations. An overview of all settings for the following preliminary experiments is shown in Table 3. For each of the following experiments, 10 independent runs were carried out.

– *Training set size:*

Similar to other machine learning methods, the training set embodies a relevant component of the CC-GP-HH algorithm. It has a significant impact on the quality of the evolved rules and in particular on their performance on independent instances from the validation set. While a small selection of problem instances might make the training set too specific, a large selection of problem instances increases the number of fitness evaluations *per* individual. Due to insufficient variety of the training set, the former can lead to so-called overfitting. Due to the high computational effort *per* generation, the latter can lead to so-called underfitting. Although the training set maps a high diversity of different problems' characteristics, only a small number of evolutions can be carried out within the limited computational time. We propose to test four different designs of the training set, covering sizes from one problem instance to 20 problem instances. The number of generations is modified accordingly to meet the limit of 500,000 total FEs.

Figure 3(a) shows that the best results of the evolved rules on the validation set can be achieved with a training set of five instances. Furthermore, the results for the training set including only one instance clearly confirm the above-discussed overfitting effect. While the evolved rules reach performances close to optimality on the training set, relatively poor results can be achieved on the validation set.

The evolved rules can therefore be stated as overfitted to the characteristics of the single instance of the training set. On the other side, for larger training set sizes of 10 and 20 instances, the consequently smaller number of generations leads to underfitted individuals. Therefore, the best allocation of the suggested 500,000 FEs can be reached with a training set of five instances and is therefore selected for further examinations.

– *Population size and number of generations:*

The population size and the number of generations can significantly influence the quality of the GP algorithm’s performance. While the number of individuals might have an impact on the population’s diversity to explore the entire space of heuristics, the number of generations typically affects the exploitation of promising individuals. Different allocations of the computational budget of 500,000 FEs are proposed to be tested and compared, varying from a population size of 100 and 1,000 generations to 1,000 individuals *per* sub-population and 100 generations.

Figure 3(b) shows the result of the candidates under investigation. Overall, the rules of 500 individuals *per* sub-population that has evolved over 200 generations revealed the best performance on both the training and validation set of instances and is therefore selected for further examinations.

– *Collaboration scheme:*

Another key feature of the CC-GP-HH represents the collaboration of individuals of sub-populations (Shi and Gao 2017). With regard to the proposed greedy heuristic to solve LSJSSPs, an individual of the sub-population for LSR must be combined with an individual of the sub-population for JSR to form a proper LSSP. Collaboration schemes can be separated into two categories (Wiegand et al. 2001). Representatives of the first category are based on randomness. The simplest way involves random shuffling of both subpopulations (Panait, Luke, and Harrison 2006). Both sub-populations are combined to generate the LSSPs. The main advantage of this method is its efficiency since each individual of both sub-populations is only evaluated once. The total number of FEs *per* generation is equal to the number of individuals of each sub-population multiplied by the training set size. Another way represents the random selection (de Oliveira et al. 2016). In contrast to the random shuffling, for each individual of each sub-population a complementing candidate from the respective other sub-population is selected randomly. This procedure is conducted for all individuals of both sub-populations. Therefore, the number of FE *per* generations is equal to the sum of individuals in both sub-populations multiplied by the training set size. The second category of collaboration schemes selects individuals based on their fitness of the previous generation. Two selection methods are tested, the tournament selection (de Oliveira et al. 2016) and the gurus selection (Glorieux et al. 2015). The gurus selection, also referred to as elite selection, combines all individuals from one sub-population with the best-performing individual of the other sub-population. For both methods, the number of fitness evaluations *per* generation is equal to the sum of individuals in both sub-populations multiplied by the training set size. The number of generations is determined in such a way as to ensure the same total number of FEs and therefore to guarantee a fair comparison.

Figure 3(c) shows the performance of the candidates under investigation. In fact, the random shuffling method showed the best results on both the training and validation set, and is therefore selected for further examinations. A possi-

Table 3. Settings for the preliminary experiments.

Experiment	Collaboration scheme	Train. size	Pop. size	#Gen.	#FEs
Training set size	Random shuffling	1	500	1,000	500,000
	Random shuffling	5	500	200	500,000
	Random shuffling	10	500	100	500,000
	Random shuffling	20	500	50	500,000
Population size and number of Generations	Random shuffling	5	100	1,000	500,000
	Random shuffling	5	200	500	500,000
	Random shuffling	5	500	200	500,000
	Random shuffling	5	1,000	100	500,000
Collaboration scheme	Random shuffling	5	500	200	500,000
	Random selection	5	500	100	500,000
	Tournament selection	5	500	100	500,000
	Gurus selection	5	500	100	500,000

Table 4. Final GP-HH settings.

Parameter	Value
#Generations	200
Population size	500 (for each sub-population)
Initial population	Ramped half-and-half (depth 2-6)
Crossover probability	90%
Maximum depth for crossover	17
Mutation rate	10%
Maximum depth for mutation	7
Collaboration scheme	Random shuffling

ble reason for that can be identified in the more efficient allocation of FEs *per* generation.

A summary of the final CC-GP-HH settings that are used for the remaining experiments is presented in Table 4.

5.2. Experimental results

This section presents and discusses the results of two consecutive experiments that differ in the design of the training sets. The aim of the CC-GP-HH method is to coevolve a combination of LSR and JSR that outperforms existing rules within the proposed greedy heuristic for LSJSSPs. In machine learning, the training set design is crucial for the learning process. Since we intend to solve a series of problem instances consisting of different shop configurations and different complexities regarding the number of products, machines, and periods, there exist two possible approaches to evolving rules: training rules for each instance class separately and generating a single rule that performs well on instances from all classes. This section is divided into two subsections, one for each experiment.

5.2.1. Experiment I: automatic evolving of specialized rules

In the first experiment, the proposed CC-GP-HH method is evaluated on each instance class separately using a set of five training instances. With the aim of automatically evolving new rules, the best rule of each run after finishing the maximum number of generations is then validated on another 10 instances of the same class. Ten indepen-

(a) Training set sizes.

(b) Population sizes and number of generations.

(c) Collaboration schemes.

Figure 3. Comparison of the performance (relative gap to CPLEX) of the best evolved rules *per run* of the preliminary experiments on the training set (left) and validation set (right).

Figure 4. Comparison of the performance (relative gap to CPLEX) of the best evolved rules *per* run of experiment I.

dent runs are carried out to ensure statistically meaningful results. The performance is measured as the gap to optimal solutions obtained by CPLEX. The results are presented in Figure 4 in the form of box plot charts, with each column representing a different JSS configuration and each row containing the results for a different number of periods. The median and mean of all 10 runs are shown, along with the best-performing combination of existing rules on each training and validation set as a benchmark.

First of all, it is worth mentioning that there is no single combination of existing rules that is superior on all instance classes in both training and validation sets. Rather, the results reveal that in total seven different combinations show the best performance in one of the classes, with only two candidates performing best in two of the classes. The first experiment aims to investigate whether the proposed CC-GP-HH can evolve rules that perform better than existing ones on validation instances from the same class as they have been trained. Results show that the evolved rules outperform the

Figure 5. Comparison of the performance (relative gap to CPLEX) of the best evolved rules *per* run of experiment II.

best-performing existing rules on the training set for all instance classes. Therefore, the functionality of the CC-GP-HH procedure’s learning process can be confirmed. On the validation set, evolved rules generally perform better than benchmark rules, especially for instances with more than 10 products, machines, and periods. However, for small-sized instances, the CC-GP-HH hardly finds better-performing rules within the predetermined settings.

5.2.2. Experiment II: automatic evolving of generalized rules

The aim of the second experiment is to investigate whether the developed CC-GP-HH method is also able to evolve generalizable rules that achieve consistent performances across all instance classes. For this purpose, we propose expanding the training set by combining the five instances from all instance classes. The training set thus includes a total of 45 instances, which cover the characteristics of different shop configurations and complexities. The validation set is modified in the same way, resulting in a total of 90 instances. The results of 10 independent runs are shown in Figure 5 in the form of a box plot chart. Please note that in this experiment only one training set containing all instance classes was examined instead of the previous nine separate training sets. The fittest rule is therefore only selected based on the average performance of all 45 instances in the training set, which means that only one boxplot is visible on the left-hand side of the figure. In addition to the performance on the training set, the achieved gap to CPLEX of the best-performing evolved rule *per* run on the validation set is also illustrated. In order to be able to better analyze the extent to which the quality of the results varies across the instance classes, the performance was additionally validated individually for each instance class. The results can be seen on the right-hand side of Figure 5 along with the best-performing combination of existing rules (*PT+WINQ / AC*).

It can be seen that the developed CC-GP-HH method is able to evolve new rules that are not only performing well on some specific instances but also are robust against a variety of different shop configurations and complexities of LSJSSPs. Compared to

the overall best existing rule $PT+WINQ / AC$, the performance of the evolved rules of all 10 runs is superior in all instance classes of the validation set.

5.3. Summary and discussion

In this section, we summarize, compare, and discuss the main results of the experiments carried out. First, the average performances *per* candidate and instance class is examined. The second part shows the essential results related to the execution time of the evolved rules. The last section analyzes the average required time for training the GP rules in experiments I and II.

5.3.1. Performance comparison

Table 5 summarizes the average performance as the relative gap to CPLEX of all tested candidates *per* instance class. Please note that for CPLEX the average optimality gap is shown instead. Except for CPLEX the best mean result across all instance classes was obtained by Experiment I. Compared to the best existing rules under investigation, the developed CC-GP-HH module was able to enhance the performance of the proposed greedy heuristic from 4.12% gap to 1.92% gap in experiment I and 2.15% gap in experiment II. Besides the improvement in the mean performance, the GP rules also show more consistent performances across all instance classes. The standard deviation could be reduced from 1.95% for the best existing rules to 1.60% in experiment I and 1.51% in experiment II. Moreover, the range of the performance was reduced from [1.72%, 8.44%] for the best existing rules to [0.41%, 4.76%] in experiment I and [0.56%, 4.20%] in experiment II. Overall, the best GP rules have beaten the best existing rules in eight out of 10 instance classes in both experiments. While the impact of the CC-GP-HH method on the performance for the small instance classes considering six products was negligibly small, relatively huge improvements were achieved for the larger instance classes containing 10 and 20 products. Only for the 6x6x10 and 6x6x20 instance classes, no better-performing rules were generated by the CC-GP-HH. Yet, the results are only slightly worse than the one of the existing rules. No significant difference could be identified between the average results of the evolved rules in experiment I and experiment II. However, the best rules of experiment I obtained superior results in five out of nine instance classes, giving experiment I a small edge over experiment II. Nevertheless, the aspect that a single generalized rule can achieve almost the same performance as a set of specialized rules should not be ignored as an advantage for experiment II.

5.3.2. Execution time comparison

Table 6 presents the average execution time *per* candidate and instance class. While CPLEX takes more than 1,400 seconds on average to solve one of the investigated LSJSSPs, the proposed greedy heuristic allows obtaining solutions within a fraction of a second. Although the average execution time of the best existing rules is almost two times shorter than for the best GP rules of experiment I and even six times shorter than the best GP rules of experiment II, in practice the absolute difference is negligible. However, the existing difference can be explained by the complexity of the rules. As defined in the GP settings, the tree structure of the evolved rules can reach a maximum depth of 17. The more complex the JSR and LSR become, the more demanding their application gets in terms of computational time. Another more significant aspect that

Table 5. Comparison of the average performance (relative gap to CPLEX, or in case of CPLEX the optimality gap) *per* problem (in %, the best values except for CPLEX are shown in bold).

	Cplex	Best existing rules	Best GP rules	
			Experiment I	Experiment II
6x6x5	0.00	5.57	2.87	4.02
6x6x10	0.30	3.95	4.76	4.06
6x6x20	1.88	3.97	4.12	4.20
10x10x5	0.00	2.36	0.41	2.01
10x10x10	0.00	3.83	1.54	1.18
10x10x20	0.00	8.44	1.13	1.11
20x5x5	0.79	1.72	0.71	0.56
20x5x10	0.74	3.37	1.19	1.20
20x5x20	0.00	3.86	0.60	0.99
Mean	0.41	4.12	1.92	2.15
Min	0.00	1.72	0.41	0.56
Max	1.88	8.44	4.76	4.20
Std Dev	0.64	1.95	1.60	1.51

Table 6. Comparison of the average execution time *per* problem (in seconds, the best values are shown in bold).

	Cplex	Best existing rules	Best GP rules	
			Experiment I	Experiment II
6x6x5	19.8376	0.0006	0.0004	0.0036
6x6x10	1236.2470	0.0013	0.0012	0.0051
6x6x20	3600.6940	0.0026	0.0052	0.0168
10x10x5	9.6892	0.0024	0.0020	0.0087
10x10x10	207.7157	0.0052	0.0040	0.0112
10x10x20	153.4814	0.0041	0.0178	0.0359
20x5x5	3260.7780	0.0048	0.0025	0.0434
20x5x10	3601.3830	0.0086	0.0061	0.0446
20x5x20	804.2782	0.0090	0.0343	0.0611
Mean	1432.6782	0.0043	0.0082	0.0256

has an impact on the execution time of the greedy heuristic represents the total number of iterations that is mainly effected by the number of periods, the number of products, and the number of machines (see algorithms in Section 4.1). The larger the LSJSSP becomes, the more time needed to construct a solution via the proposed heuristic. However, the more complex the LSJSSP to be solved becomes, the bigger the absolute difference between the execution time of CPLEX and the proposed heuristic as CPLEX takes relatively more time to solve more complex problems than the proposed heuristic does.

5.3.3. Training time comparison

Table 7 shows the average required time to evolve rules for the developed CC-GP-HH method *per* experiment. Although the training time is not as relevant as the execution time due to the fact that once a rule has been evolved, it can be applied to upcoming

Table 7. Comparison of the average training time *per* problem (in minutes, the best values are shown in bold).

	Best GP rules	
	Experiment I	Experiment II
6x6x5	42	
6x6x10	127	
6x6x20	193	
10x10x5	140	
10x10x10	136	1879
10x10x20	181	
20x5x5	464	
20x5x10	606	
20x5x20	460	
Sum	2349	1879

problems, it is worth analyzing them for the sake of completeness. In experiment I, one rule has been evolved for each instance class. The average training time varies between 42 and 606 minutes depending on the size and complexity of the instance class. In experiment II, only one rule for all instance classes has been evolved *per* run. Even though the total amount of the computation most demanding FEs is similar for both experiments, the total average training time is slightly less for experiment II. A possible explanation can be found in the remaining tasks of the algorithm. Despite the fitness evaluation, evolutionary operators such as crossover and mutation are carried out. Moreover, statistics are stored during the evolutionary process of the CC-GP-HH module. Since for all instance classes a separate rule is evolved in experiment I, the total number of runs is nine times larger than for experiment II. Therefore, all the aforementioned tasks must be carried out as well nine times which consumes a certain amount of additional computational time.

6. Conclusions

This work introduced a novel simulation-based greedy heuristic to efficiently solve complex lot-sizing and job shop scheduling problems. Making use of priority rules for both decisions regarding lot sizing and scheduling, the aim is to minimize the production, setup, and inventory holding costs. Experiments on a variety of instances considering different levels of size and complexity have been carried out. Well-known existing rules from the lot sizing and scheduling literature have been incorporated into the developed heuristic. The results proved the functionality of the proposed heuristic, while an average gap of 3.7% to CPLEX could be achieved in a fraction of a second.

To enhance the solution quality, a cooperative coevolutionary genetic programming-based hyper-heuristic method was developed. The proposed method includes a subpopulation representation, with each subpopulation responsible for either lot-sizing or scheduling. During the evolutionary process, individuals from both subpopulations collaborate with each other. Most significant parameters were analyzed in preliminary experiments, including training set size, population size, number of generations, and collaboration schemes. Employing the best-performing configurations of the algorithm, a series of experiments revealed that the CC-GP-HH method reduced the optimality gap up to 1.9%. Particularly the efficiency of the developed heuristic can be empha-

sized. Regardless of the instance size, close-optimal solutions can be obtained in a fraction of a second, while CPLEX takes on average more than 1,400 seconds to solve the problem.

A possible extension to this work represents the implementation of an improvement procedure into the simulation-based greedy heuristic to solve LSJSSPs. Boctor and Poulin (2005) for example showed that conjoining two or more lots of the same product can lead to a further reduction of the total costs. They extended their constructive procedure for solving economic lot sizing problems by additional loops to test potential cost-saving merging of lots. However, such a mechanism might consume a reasonable amount of computational time as a large number of loops must be carried out to test all potential improvements. The Experimental analysis of possible trade-offs between cost reductions and additional execution time represents an interesting study for future works.

While lot sizing problems typically focus on minimizing the total costs, the production planning and scheduling of manufacturing companies often also strive for other important objectives. Especially time-related criteria such as the makespan of the detailed schedules is a frequently studied performance measure in the field of job shop scheduling. Since the evolving JSR directly affects the time-related criteria, it would be interesting to examine the impact on those objectives. Therefore, a logical extension of our work is the consideration of multiple objectives.

Since we propose to use simulation to check the feasibility of determined lot sizes within the greedy heuristic, the entire learning process of the CC-GP-HH is computationally relatively demanding. Although the computational time for evolving rules is not as relevant as its execution time due to the fact that once a rule has been evolved it can be applied to solve upcoming problems, the implementation of surrogates for approximating the fitness of individuals instead of conducting the entire constructive procedure during the learning process represents a promising prospect for future work.

In fact, one of the biggest advantages of the presented greedy heuristic is its short execution time of far less than one second. To this end, we believe that the procedure is particularly useful for dynamic environments in which frequent replanning and rescheduling are inevitable. Uncertainties such as fluctuating customer demand enforce recurrent updates of the production plan and schedules. A fast generation of new solutions is therefore of utmost importance to enable practical use in real-world manufacturing systems. Hence, future research on the implementation of our approach into a rolling horizon planning scheme and its validation on real industrial case studies seems to be another promising avenue.

Acknowledgements

Yannik Zeiträg acknowledges the support by national funds through FCT (Fundação para a Ciência e a Tecnologia), reference: BD/05314/2021. José Rui Figueira acknowledges the support by national funds through Fundação para a Ciência e a Tecnologia under the DOME research project, PTDC/CCI-COM/31198/2017. Yannik Zeiträg and José Rui Figueira acknowledge the Portuguese national funds through the FCT - Foundation for Science and Technology, I.P., under the project UIDB/00097/2020. Gonçalo Figueira acknowledges the support from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the TRUST-AI research project, grant agreement No 952060.

Disclosure statement

The authors report there are no competing interests to declare.

References

- Abdollahzadeh Sangroudi, Hadi, and Mehdi Ranjbar-Bourani. 2021. "Solving a flexible job shop lot sizing problem with shared operations using a self-adaptive COA." *International Journal of Production Research* 59 (2): 483–515.
- Abednego, Luciana, and Dwi Hendratmo. 2011. "Genetic programming hyper-heuristic for solving dynamic production scheduling problem." In *Electrical Engineering and Informatics (ICEEI), 2011 International Conference on*, 1–4. IEEE / Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers Incorporated.
- Afentakis, Panos. 1985. "Simultaneous lot sizing and sequencing for multistage production systems." *IIE transactions* 17 (4): 327–331.
- Blackstone, John H., D. T.O.N. Phillips, and GARY L. Hogg. 1982. "A state-of-the-art survey of dispatching rules for manufacturing job shop operations." *International Journal of Production Research* 20 (1): 27–45.
- Boctor, Fayez F, and Patrice Poulin. 2005. "Heuristics for the N-product, M-stage, economic lot sizing and scheduling problem with dynamic demand." *International journal of production research* 43 (13): 2809–2828.
- Branke, Jurgen, Su Nguyen, Christoph W. Pickardt, and Mengjie Zhang. 2016. "Automated Design of Production Scheduling Heuristics: A Review." *IEEE Transactions on Evolutionary Computation* 20 (1): 110–124.
- Burke, Edmund, Graham Kendall, Jim Newall, Emma Hart, Peter Ross, and Sonia Schulenburg. 2003. "Hyper-Heuristics: An Emerging Direction in Modern Search Technology." In *Handbook of metaheuristics*, edited by Fred Glover and Gary A. Kochenberger, Vol. 57 of *International Series in Operations Research & Management Science*, 457–474. Boston and London: Kluwer Academic Publishers.
- Buschkühl, Lisbeth, Florian Sahling, Stefan Helber, and Horst Tempelmeier. 2010. "Dynamic capacitated lot-sizing problems: a classification and review of solution approaches." *Or Spectrum* 32 (2): 231–261.
- Castro, Pedro M, Ignacio E Grossmann, and Qi Zhang. 2018. "Expanding scope and computational challenges in process scheduling." *Computers & Chemical Engineering* 114: 14–42.
- Dabbas, Russ M, and John W Fowler. 2003. "A new scheduling approach using combined dispatching criteria in wafer fabs." *IEEE Transactions on semiconductor manufacturing* 16 (3): 501–510.
- Dauzere-Peres, Stephane, and Jean-Bernard Lasserre. 1994. "Integration of lotsizing and scheduling decisions in a job-shop." *European Journal of Operational Research* 75 (2): 413–426.
- de Oliveira, Fernando Bernardes, Rasul Enayatifar, Hossein Javedani Sadaei, Frederico Gadelha Guimarães, and Jean-Yves Potvin. 2016. "A cooperative coevolutionary algorithm for the multi-depot vehicle routing problem." *Expert Systems with Applications* 43: 117–130.
- DeMatteis, John J. 1968. "An economic lot-sizing technique, I: The part-period algorithm." *IBM systems Journal* 7 (1): 30–38.
- Dimopoulos, C., and A.M.S. Zalzalá. 2001. "Investigating the use of genetic programming for a classic one-machine scheduling problem." *Advances in Engineering Software* 32 (6): 489–498.
- Dixon, Paul S, and Edward A Silver. 1981. "A heuristic solution procedure for the multi-item, single-level, limited capacity, lot-sizing problem." *Journal of Operations Management* 2 (1): 23–39.

- Dogramaci, Ali, John C Panayiotopoulos, and Nabil R Adam. 1981. "The dynamic lot-sizing problem for multiple items under limited capacity." *AIIE transactions* 13 (4): 294–303.
- Eisenhut, PS. 1975. "A dynamic lot sizing algorithm with capacity constraints." *AIIE transactions* 7 (2): 170–176.
- Ferreira, Cristiane, Gonçalo Figueira, and Pedro Amorim. 2022. "Effective and interpretable dispatching rules for dynamic job shops via guided empirical learning." *Omega* 111: 102643.
- Fisher, H., and G. L. Thompson. 1963. "Probabilistic Learning Combinations of Local Job-Shop Scheduling Rules." *Industrial scheduling* 225–251.
- Geiger, Christopher D., Reha Uzsoy, and Haldun Aytug. 2006. "Rapid Modeling and Discovery of Priority Dispatching Rules: An Autonomous Learning Approach." *Journal of Scheduling* 9 (1): 7–34.
- Giglio, Davide, Massimo Paolucci, and Abdolreza Roshani. 2017. "Integrated lot sizing and energy-efficient job shop scheduling problem in manufacturing/remanufacturing systems." *Journal of cleaner production* 148: 624–641.
- Glorieux, Emile, Bo Svensson, Fredrik Danielsson, and Bengt Lennartson. 2015. "Improved constructive cooperative coevolutionary differential evolution for large-scale optimisation." In *2015 IEEE symposium series on computational intelligence*, 1703–1710. IEEE.
- Gomez Urrutia, Edwin David, Riad Aggoune, and Stéphane Dauzère-Pères. 2014. "Solving the integrated lot-sizing and job-shop scheduling problem." *International Journal of Production Research* 52 (17): 5236–5254.
- Groff, G.K. 1979. "A lot sizing rule for time phased component demand." *Prod, Invent. Mgmt* 20: 66.
- Gupta, Diwakar, and Thorkell Magnusson. 2005. "The capacitated lot-sizing and scheduling problem with sequence-dependent setup costs and setup times." *Computers & Operations Research* 32 (4): 727–747.
- Günther, H.O. 1987. "Planning lot sizes and capacity requirements in a single stage production system." *European Journal of Operational Research* 31 (2): 223–231. First EURO VII special issue: Location and transportation problems production systems.
- Hein, Fanny, Christian Almeder, Gonçalo Figueira, and Bernardo Almada-Lobo. 2018. "Designing new heuristics for the capacitated lot sizing problem by genetic programming." *Computers & Operations Research* 96: 1–14.
- Helber, Stefan. 1995. "Lot sizing in capacitated production planning and control systems." *Operations-Research-Spektrum* 17 (1): 5–18.
- Ho, NhuBinh, and Joc Cing Tay. 2005. "Evolving Dispatching Rules for solving the Flexible Job-Shop Problem." In *The 2005 IEEE Congress on Evolutionary Computation*, Piscataway, 2848–2855. IEEE.
- Holthaus, Oliver, and Chandrasekharan Rajendran. 1997. "Efficient dispatching rules for scheduling in a job shop." *International Journal of Production Economics* 48 (1): 87–105.
- Jakobović, Domagoj, Leonardo Jelenković, and Leo Budin. 2007. "Genetic Programming Heuristics for Multiple Machine Scheduling." In *Genetic programming*, edited by Marc Ebner, Vol. 4445 of *Lecture notes in computer science, 0302-9743*, 321–330. Berlin: Springer.
- Jayamohan, MS, and Chandrasekharan Rajendran. 2004. "Development and analysis of cost-based dispatching rules for job shop scheduling." *European journal of operational research* 157 (2): 307–321.
- Karni, Reuven, and Yaakov Roll. 1982. "A heuristic algorithm for the multi-item lot-sizing problem with capacity constraints." *IIE Transactions* 14 (4): 249–256.
- Koza, John R. 1992. *Genetic Programming: On the Programming of Computers by Means of Natural Selection*. A Bradford book. Cambridge, Mass.: MIT Press.
- Lambrecht, MR, and H Vanderveken. 1979. "Heuristic procedures for the single operation, multi-item loading problem." *AIIE Transactions* 11 (4): 319–326.
- Luke, Sean. 1998. "ECJ Evolutionary Computation Library." Available for free at <http://cs.gmu.edu/~eclab/projects/ecj/>.
- Maes, Johan, and Luk N. Van Wassenhove. 1986. "A simple heuristic for the multi item single level capacitated lotsizing problem." *Operations Research Letters* 4 (6): 265–273.

- Maravelias, Christos T., and Charles Sung. 2009. "Integration of production planning and scheduling: Overview, challenges and opportunities." *Computers Chemical Engineering* 33 (12): 1919–1930. FOCAPO 2008 – Selected Papers from the Fifth International Conference on Foundations of Computer-Aided Process Operations.
- Masood, Atiya, Yi Mei, Gang Chen, and Mengjie Zhang. 2017. "A PSO-Based Reference Point Adaption Method for Genetic Programming Hyper-Heuristic in Many-Objective Job Shop Scheduling." In *Artificial life and computational intelligence*, edited by Markus Wagner, Xiaodong Li, and Tim Hendtlass, Vol. 10142 of *LNCS Sublibrary: SL7 - Artificial Intelligence*, 326–338. Cham: Springer.
- Miettinen, Kaisa, Francisco Ruiz, and Andrzej P. Wierzbicki. 2008. *Introduction to Multi-objective Optimization: Interactive Approaches*, 27–57. Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer Berlin Heidelberg.
- Moore, JM, and RC Wilson. 1967. "A review of simulation research in job shop scheduling." *Production and Inventory Management* 8 (1): 1–10.
- Nguyen, Su, Yi Mei, and Mengjie Zhang. 2017. "Genetic programming for production scheduling: a survey with a unified framework." *Complex & Intelligent Systems* 3: 41–66.
- Nguyen, Su, Mengjie Zhang, Mark Johnston, and Kay Chen Tan. 2013. "Dynamic Multi-objective Job Shop Scheduling: A Genetic Programming Approach." In *Automated scheduling and planning*, edited by A. Şima Etaner-Uyar, Ender Özcan, and Neil Urquhart, Vol. 505 of *Studies in computational intelligence, 1860-949X*, 251–282. Heidelberg: Springer.
- Panait, Liviu, Sean Luke, and Joseph F Harrison. 2006. "Archive-based cooperative coevolutionary algorithms." In *Proceedings of the 8th annual conference on Genetic and evolutionary computation*, 345–352.
- Panwalker, S. S., and Wafik Iskander. 1977. "A Survey of Scheduling Rules." *Operations Research* 25 (1): 45–61.
- Park, John, Yi Mei, Su Nguyen, Gang Chen, and Mengjie Zhang. 2018. "An investigation of ensemble combination schemes for genetic programming based hyper-heuristic approaches to dynamic job shop scheduling." *Applied Soft Computing* 63: 72–86.
- Pickardt, Christoph W, and Jürgen Branke. 2012. "Setup-oriented dispatching rules—a survey." *International Journal of Production Research* 50 (20): 5823–5842.
- Pickardt, Christoph W., Torsten Hildebrandt, Jürgen Branke, Jens Heger, and Bernd Scholz-Reiter. 2013. "Evolutionary generation of dispatching rule sets for complex dynamic scheduling problems." *International Journal of Production Economics* 145 (1): 67–77.
- Rajendran, Chandrasekharan, and Oliver Holthaus. 1999. "A comparative study of dispatching rules in dynamic flowshops and jobshops." *European Journal of Operational Research* 116 (1): 156–170.
- Rohaninejad, Mohammad, Mikoláš Janota, and Zdeněk Hanzálek. 2023. "Integrated lot-sizing and scheduling: Mitigation of uncertainty in demand and processing time by machine learning." *Engineering Applications of Artificial Intelligence* 118: 105676.
- Shen, W., L. Wang, and Q. Hao. 2006. "Agent-based distributed manufacturing process planning and scheduling: A state-of-the-art survey." *IEEE Transactions on Systems, Man and Cybernetics Part C: Applications and Reviews* 36 (4): 563–577.
- Shi, Min, and Shang Gao. 2017. "Reference sharing: a new collaboration model for cooperative coevolution." *Journal of Heuristics* 23: 1–30.
- Silver, E.A., and H.C. Meal. 1973. "A heuristic for selecting lot size quantities for the case of a deterministic time-varying demand rate and discrete opportunities for replenishment." *Prod. Invent. Mgmt* 14 (2): 64 – 74.
- Tan, W., and B. Khoshnevis. 2000. "Integration of process planning and scheduling—a review." *Journal of Intelligent Manufacturing* 11 (1): 51–63.
- Tay, Joc Cing, and Nhu Binh Ho. 2008. "Evolving dispatching rules using genetic programming for solving multi-objective flexible job-shop problems." *Computers & Industrial Engineering* 54 (3): 453–473.
- Tempelmeier, Horst, and Stefan Helber. 1994. "A heuristic for dynamic multi-item multi-level capacitated lotsizing for general product structures." *European Journal of Operational*

- Research* 75 (2): 296–311.
- Trigeiro, William W. 1989. “A simple heuristic for lot sizing with setup times.” *Decision Sciences* 20 (2): 294–303.
- Van Nunen, JAEE, and Jaap Wessels. 1978. “Multi-item lot size determination and scheduling under capacity constraints.” *European Journal of Operational Research* 2 (1): 36–41.
- Wagner, Harvey M, and Thomson M Whitin. 1958. “Dynamic version of the economic lot size model.” *Management science* 5 (1): 89–96.
- Wiegand, R Paul, William C Liles, Kenneth A De Jong, et al. 2001. “An empirical analysis of collaboration methods in cooperative coevolutionary algorithms.” In *Proceedings of the genetic and evolutionary computation conference (GECCO)*, Vol. 2611, 1235–1245. Morgan Kaufmann San Francisco.
- Wolosewicz, Cathy, Stéphane Dauzère-Pérès, and Riad Aggoune. 2015. “A Lagrangian heuristic for an integrated lot-sizing and fixed scheduling problem.” *European Journal of Operational Research* 244 (1): 3–12.
- Zeiträg, Yannik, José Rui Figueira, Nuno Horta, and Rui Neves. 2022. “Surrogate-assisted automatic evolving of dispatching rules for multi-objective dynamic job shop scheduling using genetic programming.” *Expert Systems with Applications* 209: 118194.
- Zhang, Fangfang, Yi Mei, and Mengjie Zhang. 2019. “Evolving Dispatching Rules for Multi-objective Dynamic Flexible Job Shop Scheduling via Genetic Programming Hyper-heuristics.” In *2019 IEEE Congress on Evolutionary Computation (CEC)*, 1366–1373.
- Zhou, Yong, Jian-jun Yang, and Zhuang Huang. 2020. “Automatic design of scheduling policies for dynamic flexible job shop scheduling via surrogate-assisted cooperative co-evolution genetic programming.” *International Journal of Production Research* 58 (9): 2561–2580.

Appendix A. Terminals and functions

Table A1. Terminal and function set.

Type	Symbol	Description	
Terminals	PT	Processing time of an operation	
JSR	RT	Release time of a job	
	RPT	Remaining processing time of a job	
	RNO	Remaining number of uncompleted operations of a job	
	DD	Due date of a job	
	RTO	Ready time of an operation	
	PTN	Processing time of the next operation	
	SL	Slack of the job = $DD - (CT + RPT)$	
	WT	Waiting time of the operation = $\max(0, CT - RTO)$	
	APTQ	Average processing time of operations of waiting jobs	
	NJQ	Number of waiting jobs in the queue	
	WINQ	Work in next queue	
	CT	Current time	
	Terminals	AHC	Additional holding costs incurred with the lot extension of product i
LSR	BSV	Binary setup variable; 1 if product i is set up in period ℓ , 0 otherwise	
	SC	Setup cost of product i	
	CF	Capacity gap in period ℓ	
	NPRC	Number of periods requirements the current lot of product i satisfies	
	HCC	Holding costs incurred with the current lot of product i	
	NPRE	Number of periods requirements the extended lot of product i satisfies	
	CU	Capacity usage to produce one unit of product i	
	ADSHC	Absolute deviation between setup and holding costs incurred with the current lot of product i	
	APDR	Average period demand of product i considering remaining periods from $\ell + 1$ to u	
	NP	Number of products	
	LPH	Length of the planning horizon	
	CP	Current period ℓ in which lot-sizes are extended	
	HC	Holding cost <i>per</i> unit of product i	
	APD	Average period demand of product i	
	APDN	Average period demand over n products	
	TBO	Time between two orders based on the average period demand	
	SHC	Setup over holding costs	
	SHCN	SHC normalized by the average demand	
	C	Capacity in period ℓ	
	CLS	Current lot size of product i satisfying NPRC periods requirements	
	PLE	Potential lot extension of product i (i.e. demand in period $\ell + NPRC$)	
	RCC	Remaining cumulated capacity from period $\ell + 1$ to u	
	ADSHCE	Absolute deviation between setup and holding costs incurred with the extended lot of product i	
	Functions	ADD	Addition
	JSR/LSR	SUB	Subtraction
		MUL	Multiplication
DIV		Protected division ($DIV(a, b) = 1$, if $b = 0$)	
MAX		Maximum	
MIN		Minimum	
IFTE		Ternary operator “if-then-else” ($IFTE(a, b, c) = b$, if $a > 0$, c otherwise)	

Appendix B. Results Cplex

Table B1. Results obtained by CPLEX within a time limit of one hour (in total costs).

Problem	Training set					Validation set									
	1	2	3	4	5	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
6x6x5	1117	1189	1209	1206	1135	1163	1208	1168	1202	1119	1086	1141	1183	1210	1141
6x6x10	2335*	2202	2314	2313	2340	2395*	2284	2257	2343*	2236	2313	2161	2298	2315	2265
6x6x20	3422*	3392*	3354*	3217*	3143*	3328*	3462*	3310*	3369*	3380*	3231*	3396*	3301*	3286*	3399*
10x10x5	1943	1834	2009	1819	2007	1870	2030	1859	1935	1819	1917	1843	2005	2022	1825
10x10x10	3818	3711	3753	3727	3697	3734	3701	3702	3660	3774	3734	3918	3717	3674	3627
10x10x20	4706	4784	4897	4707	4658	4602	4782	4608	4750	4725	4771	4880	4835	4779	4705
20x5x5	3897*	3931*	3747*	3841*	3772*	3927*	3808*	3931*	3775*	3870*	3788*	3753*	3744*	3783	3793*
20x5x10	7655*	7453*	7283*	7494*	7546*	7631*	7457*	7454*	7594*	7544*	7548*	7527*	7598*	7470*	7623*
20x5x20	18122	18138	18407	18349	18327	18146	17844	18087	18137	18184	18224	18124	18276	18058*	18334

* no optimal solution obtained within the time limit of one hour (gap < 4%)

Appendix C. Results existing rules

Table C1. Comparison of the average performance (relative gap to CPLEX) *per* instance class of the training set (validation set) (in %, the best values are shown in bold).

Rules (JSR / LSR)	Training set (validation set)										Mean
	6x6x5	6x6x10	6x6x20	10x10x5	10x10x10	10x10x20	20x5x5	20x5x10	20x5x20		
SPT / DS	33.66 (32.84)	34.77 (35.2)	57.67 (57.38)	36.6 (36.76)	39.58 (39.83)	43.08 (43.17)	35.92 (36.27)	38.94 (38.47)	20.92 (21.25)	37.9 (37.91)	
SPT / E	16.18 (14.41)	13.81 (14.91)	20.53 (22.3)	18.16 (18.52)	30.47 (33.65)	38.03 (37.13)	16.68 (17.27)	26.88 (30.63)	24.38 (25.65)	22.79 (23.83)	
SPT / GR	4.26 (5.27)	5.21 (4.29)	4.68 (4.14)	2.91 (2.45)	4.69 (4.77)	12.8 (12.67)	2.49 (3.24)	5.07 (5.75)	22.4 (22.38)	7.17 (7.22)	
SPT / LUC	6.37 (6.39)	6.73 (6.11)	6.99 (6.68)	4.64 (5.25)	8.2 (7.2)	11.08 (13.05)	5.52 (5.71)	10.44 (11.19)	5.86 (5.77)	7.31 (7.48)	
SPT / AC	4.91 (6)	4.14 (5.24)	4.41 (3.97)	2.82 (2.47)	5.48 (4.97)	7.79 (8.53)	1.53 (1.57)	3.7 (4.19)	3.63 (3.86)	4.27 (4.53)	
SPT / R	61.16 (46.55)	100.3 (104.33)	167.67 (205.14)	107.94 (109.41)	276.88 (277.36)	664.26 (673.44)	79.26 (76.24)	186.08 (183.11)	384.11 (367.04)	225.3 (226.96)	
FIFO / DS	33.66 (32.84)	34.77 (35.2)	57.67 (57.38)	36.6 (36.76)	39.58 (39.83)	43.08 (43.17)	35.92 (36.27)	38.94 (38.47)	20.92 (21.25)	37.9 (37.91)	
FIFO / E	12.25 (16.8)	15.89 (15.58)	20.9 (22.64)	15.66 (17.96)	31.49 (31.15)	38.1 (37.26)	16.39 (15.98)	26.93 (31.52)	25.19 (25.62)	22.53 (23.83)	
FIFO / GR	5.57 (6.08)	4.05 (3.95)	4.98 (5.12)	1.81 (2.36)	4.19 (3.76)	11.69 (11.89)	3.89 (3.69)	5.21 (4.81)	22.03 (19.24)	7.05 (6.77)	
FIFO / LUC	4.9 (7.17)	6.69 (5.33)	6.49 (7.94)	4.2 (4.86)	7.3 (7.02)	11.61 (11.86)	5.67 (5.82)	10.23 (9.17)	5.88 (5.8)	7 (7.22)	
FIFO / AC	5.36 (5.31)	4.25 (4.08)	5.6 (4.31)	2.12 (2.4)	3.98 (4.7)	8.06 (8.4)	0.97 (1.72)	3.96 (3.97)	3.62 (3.65)	4.21 (4.28)	
FIFO / R	54.9 (46.96)	105.31 (102.57)	169.29 (194.54)	111.4 (115.55)	285.53 (273.75)	678.81 (654.56)	80.63 (81.16)	186.88 (197.03)	406.3 (395.96)	231.01 (229.12)	
MTWR / DS	33.66 (49.32)	34.77 (35.2)	57.67 (57.38)	36.6 (36.76)	39.58 (39.83)	43.08 (43.17)	35.92 (36.27)	38.94 (38.47)	20.92 (21.25)	37.9 (39.74)	
MTWR / E	13.86 (15.19)	16.18 (16.64)	20.95 (22.81)	18.22 (17.95)	31.74 (31.86)	37.84 (37.71)	16.86 (16.76)	25.86 (30.19)	24.92 (25.79)	22.94 (23.88)	
MTWR / GR	6.38 (5.61)	5.09 (4.84)	6.43 (4.26)	2.37 (2.32)	4.97 (5.53)	13.08 (13.85)	3.14 (3.84)	5.78 (6.18)	21.33 (21.61)	7.62 (7.56)	
MTWR / LUC	7 (6.32)	7.15 (6.25)	8.49 (6.83)	5.52 (4.77)	6.85 (7.5)	9.83 (11.26)	6.66 (6.23)	9.61 (11.14)	8.2 (5.77)	7.7 (7.34)	
MTWR / AC	5.74 (6)	5.88 (4.84)	4.5 (5.38)	2.23 (2.58)	5.03 (5.06)	7.3 (8.44)	2.29 (2.92)	4.19 (4.07)	3.56 (3.86)	4.52 (4.79)	
MTWR / R	50.54 (45.78)	96.36 (101.44)	164.23 (193.02)	104.36 (105.51)	276.77 (266.29)	659.72 (645.07)	75.41 (72.26)	170.64 (171.64)	362.8 (351.39)	217.87 (216.93)	
WINQ / DS	33.66 (32.84)	34.77 (35.2)	57.67 (57.38)	36.6 (36.76)	39.58 (39.83)	43.08 (43.17)	35.92 (36.27)	38.94 (38.47)	20.92 (21.25)	37.9 (37.91)	
WINQ / E	13.02 (14.29)	15.49 (15.24)	21.53 (23.09)	17.85 (18.71)	31.94 (31.32)	37.31 (36.97)	15.64 (15.06)	26.88 (31.65)	24.33 (25.73)	22.67 (23.56)	
WINQ / GR	5.59 (5.37)	5.01 (4.61)	5.95 (4.74)	2.19 (2.35)	3.85 (3.83)	12.2 (11.94)	2.92 (3.54)	4.13 (4.67)	21.42 (20.59)	7.03 (6.85)	
WINQ / LUC	5.09 (6.57)	7.36 (6.63)	7.84 (6.58)	4.64 (4.77)	6.34 (7.94)	11.85 (12.69)	5.88 (6.07)	10.69 (10.12)	5.89 (6.4)	7.29 (7.53)	
WINQ / AC	4.78 (5.05)	4.79 (4.49)	6.07 (4.86)	2.16 (2.46)	4.67 (4.53)	7.45 (8.25)	1.65 (1.1)	3.4 (3.37)	3.71 (3.71)	4.3 (4.2)	
WINQ / R	58.81 (47.05)	110.69 (105.77)	178.46 (200.68)	112.54 (115.73)	274.85 (278.6)	690.13 (665.87)	82.94 (83.28)	189.47 (195.38)	412.43 (394.19)	234.48 (231.84)	
PT+WINQ / DS	33.66 (32.84)	34.77 (35.2)	57.67 (57.38)	36.6 (36.76)	39.58 (39.83)	43.08 (43.17)	35.92 (36.27)	38.94 (38.47)	20.92 (21.25)	37.9 (37.91)	
PT+WINQ / E	14.17 (16.03)	12.92 (16.05)	21.15 (22)	16.83 (17.97)	29.77 (32.14)	38.59 (37.71)	16.94 (15.55)	26.01 (32.46)	24.91 (25.7)	22.37 (23.96)	
PT+WINQ / GR	4.69 (6.34)	4.74 (5.07)	5.27 (4.55)	1.95 (2.37)	4.29 (4.71)	12.45 (13.38)	2.26 (3.2)	4.54 (5.83)	22.43 (23.64)	6.96 (7.68)	
PT+WINQ / LUC	6.39 (6.02)	7.84 (6.75)	8.64 (7.07)	4.3 (5)	7.26 (7.43)	11.1 (12.85)	5.24 (5.52)	10.63 (9.76)	6.75 (5.94)	7.57 (7.37)	
PT+WINQ / AC	3.99 (5.57)	4.27 (5.05)	5.11 (5.07)	2.95 (2.52)	4.32 (4.54)	7.41 (8.39)	1.71 (1.81)	4.15 (4.02)	3.75 (3.74)	4.18 (4.52)	
PT+WINQ / R	61.9 (46.4)	100.91 (105.48)	171.02 (203.63)	111.91 (112.03)	283.76 (281.66)	682.16 (678.98)	81.31 (80.88)	185.02 (194.96)	402.27 (382.66)	231.14 (231.85)	
R / DS	33.66 (32.84)	34.77 (35.2)	57.67 (57.38)	36.6 (36.76)	39.58 (39.83)	43.08 (43.17)	35.92 (36.27)	38.94 (38.47)	20.92 (21.25)	37.9 (37.91)	
R / E	14.96 (14.62)	13.69 (16.72)	21.42 (22.87)	15.1 (18.74)	30.79 (30.78)	38.93 (36.98)	17.5 (16.72)	24.79 (30.49)	24.26 (25.73)	22.38 (23.74)	
R / GR	6.16 (5.51)	4.41 (4.39)	4.73 (4.16)	2.31 (2.03)	4.31 (4.61)	11.34 (13.4)	2.68 (2.84)	4.82 (5.1)	23.99 (24.66)	7.19 (7.41)	
R / LUC	6.21 (5.95)	7 (6.74)	7.96 (6.88)	5.18 (5.42)	7.31 (8.66)	11.89 (12.46)	6 (5.81)	9.79 (11.09)	6.66 (5.75)	7.56 (7.64)	
R / AC	4.87 (3.56)	4.58 (5)	5.93 (4.46)	2.31 (2.51)	4.07 (4.61)	8.19 (8.44)	1.96 (1.92)	3.58 (4.04)	3.81 (3.79)	4.37 (4.26)	
R / R	59.69 (43.22)	99.48 (106.09)	190.14 (205.9)	107.88 (108.72)	282.23 (270.91)	665.41 (662.99)	80.15 (79.93)	185.09 (192.75)	399.1 (385.41)	229.91 (228.44)	